

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Deliverable D2.1: Report on the concept for the Database and monitoring system & report on implementation

AUTHORS	Alexander Gocht (Thünen), Sebastian Neuenfeldt (Thünen), Marc Müller (WR)
APPROVED BY WP MANAGER:	Alexander Gocht (Thünen)
DATE OF APPROVAL:	15.11.2024
APPROVED BY PROJECT COORDINATOR:	Marc Müller (WR)
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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CIRCABC	An EU open-source platform, enables secure, collaborative information sharing
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DokuWiki	Collaborative Documentation Platform
EC	European Commission
ECA	European Court of Auditors
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FMU	Farm Mapping units
GeoCMS	Geospatial Content Management System
GeoNode	Open-source Geospatial Content Management System
Git	Distributed Version Control System
HBS	Household budget surveys
HSMU	Homogenous spatial mapping units
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
JavaScript	An object-oriented computer programming language commonly used to create interactive effects within web browser
LPIS	Land Parcel Identification System
Markup	A text-encoding system which specifies the structure and formatting of a document and potentially the relationship between its parts
MRS	Multiresolution segmentation
MS	Member States
NTM	Non-Tariff Measures
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
Observable	Tool for visualizing tabular data, focused on accelerating exploratory data analysis.
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
Python	An interpreted, object-oriented, high-level programming language with dynamic semantics
R	A programming language for statistical computing and data visualization

SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructures
SILC	Statistics on income and living conditions
SJOS	Safe and Just Operating Space
SSG	Static Site Generator
Vitepress	SSG designed for building fast, content-centric websites
WP	Work Package
Zenodo	Open-access Repository

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report delineates the comprehensive concept and implementation process of the BrightSpace Database and Monitoring System (BSDMS), to ensure efficient version control, real-time visualization, and open access to data. BSDMS is focusing on three fundamental aspects: collaboration and transparency through code sharing, result presentation, and data dissemination. Leveraging tools like Git for code collaboration, Observable for interactive result presentations, DokuWiki or Vitepress for collaborative documentation, and platforms like GeoNode and Zenodo for geospatial data visualization and hosting.

The report outlines the requirements of BSDMS, emphasizing its organization by thematic fields of Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS) to provide transparent access to relevant data. BSDMS is designed to be a “living document” that is freely accessible yet has restricted areas to ensure ownership and access rights for project partners while adhering to strict data protection rules.

Technological overviews of crucial tools such as Git, Observable, DokuWiki, Vitepress, open-source geospatial content management systems (GeoCMS) like GeoNode, and repositories like Zenodo are provided. Git facilitates collaborative software development with its robust version control capabilities, while Observable enables real-time data visualization and collaborative code editing. DokuWiki or Vitepress offers a simple yet versatile platform for collaborative documentation or is alternatively complemented by WordPress's flexibility and extensive plugin ecosystem. Open-source GeoCMS like GeoNode and repositories like Zenodo ensure the management, sharing, and preservation of geospatial data and research outputs, promoting collaboration, transparency, and open science practices.

A proposal is made on how the implementation plan to open data can be guided and what specific SJOS data or indicator is suitable to be made available via platforms like GIT, Observable, GeoCMS, or Zenodo.

2. INTRODUCTION

This report aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the database and monitoring system concept, along with insights into the implementation process. The report will focus on three key elements of dissemination and communication about the BRIGHTSPACE Database and Monitoring System: collaborating on and being transparent about code, presenting results, and sharing data and results. All three elements shall be connected and visible through an open-access documentation platform. In this work package, it is not envisaged that existing data will be collected and published. Rather, it is envisaged that information on already existing data and where it can be found should be provided. Further, it should assemble that information close to the Safe and Just operating space topics that are central to the BRIGHTSPACE project. Data, that will be produced by partners within BrightSpace, will also be part of the database.

One available collaboration and code-sharing tool is GIT, which will be explained later. Presenting results, focusing on explaining results, will be made possible with Observable. Data and results will be made feasible by sharing with, for instance, Geonode (open-source geospatial content management system for visualization) and Zenodo (data host). All this will be accessible via a platform like DokuWiki or Vitepress, which serves as a tool for describing and linking the elements mentioned above. This platform is highly flexible in how it is presented. Therefore, a specific focus on the BRIGHTSPACE immanent topic of Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS) will be present throughout the presentation to guide users to the relevant indicators and how the project's partner worked and produced results.

The different tools (Git, Observable, DokuWiki, etc.) will be presented, along with their roles, advantages, and implementation considerations. Subsequently, the whole implementation plan will be outlined.

For the annual meeting 2023, the partners were asked to provide information regarding their status quo of data acquisition, processing of the data, results production, and publication of it. Data for SAFE and JUST space separate the tables; the SAFE space is further divided by novel spatial data for agriculture. Each row in the table stands for one specific SJOS topic or indicator and is connected with a task of a work package (in brackets). The columns further comprise the scale of the data (global, regional, etc.), the status of the work (started, completed), the responsible partner, the intention of whether parts of the work are to be implemented in the IIASA data toolbox, and the current state of play regarding the topic. To provide some understanding, we added topic values in the cells based on what could be finished already.

Table 1. Overview of Task 2.2: Database and Monitoring System for SAFE space across spatial scales

Task	Data or processes required for evidence on SJOS	Resolution	Work started	Responsibility	Data toolbox	Comments regarding the current status
4.2	Non-Tariff Measures	global, country	YES	CITA	Yes, the original data, subject to authorization	EU and FAO-WHO Codex Alimentarius dataset on pesticides downloaded and screened for further use in econometric models. The UNCTAD-TRAINS NTMs database has been matched with bilateral trade data (UN ComTrade) at HS6 digits (720 products), for a panel between 2010-2020. RASFF database has been downloaded and we are in the process of matching with HS6 nomenclature.
3.3	Food Waste and Losses along the Supply Chain	EU MSs	YES	CITA, WU	Yes, the original data, subject to authorization	<p>Database extracted from De Laurentiis et al (2023). Data comprises estimated food loss and waste along the chain by product disaggregation level for each of the EU Member States for the period 2003-2020. Estimated data are available in a public domain area: http://data.europa.eu/89h/a86ae681-f051-4809-85f3-5fa0ad7b25ee</p> <p>Drivers according to the literature and extracted from open access sources, as an example:</p> <p>Population is available at:</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_pjan__custom_10368095/default/table</p> <p>Real GDP per capita is available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_08_10/default/table</p> <p>Unemployment rate is available at:</p>

						<p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tps00203__custom_10340859/default/table</p> <p>The databases have been merged, and preliminary statistical analysis has been conducted, along with the initial stages of econometric analysis yielding some preliminary results.</p>
	CAP and CMEF Indicators	EU, country level	Yes	WR	As downloaded	<p>Cap context and result indicators were downloaded and compared as an important input for the definition of the Safe and Just operating space.</p> <p>Download links:</p> <p>https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DashboardCapPlan/result_indicators.html</p> <p>https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DataPortal/context_indicators.html</p>
	Organic farming	Regional, farm typology	Yes	WR		<p>The FADN data received in April 2024 are by default split in organic (fully converted) and conventional to permit a statistical analysis of productivity and intensity differences between these two farm specializations and to generate input data for the FarmDyn model.</p>
3.3	Dietary developments	global, country	Yes	TI/EuroCare	yes	<p>Improved application of lancet diet shifts in raw product models; Application for EFSA consumer data ongoing. Food intake quantities stem from the German National Nutrition Survey II (NVSII) from 2006 with 13,926 randomly selected participants, representative of the German-speaking population, between the ages of 14 and 80 questioned in 24h-recalls about their intake of food and beverages (Brombach et al., 2006; Krems et al., 2006). The participants were selected randomly in around 500 municipalities and are representative of the German-speaking population. The 24h-recalls are available at EFSA’s comprehensive food consumption database (EFSA, 2023).</p>

	Biodiversity, Water, Nitrogen	regional		IIASA	maybe	This dataset comprises spatial biophysical data regarding aspect, elevation and slope derived from https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/collections/copernicus-digital-elevation-model and topsoil properties derived from https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/topsoil-physical-properties-europe-based-lucas-topsoil-data to the NUTS regions across Europe. The dataset consists of two files, each corresponding to a different level of NUTS coding (NUTS 2/3).
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Table 2. Overview of Task 2.3: Database and Monitoring System for JOS across spatial scales

Task	Data or processes required for evidence on SJOS	Resolution	Work started	Responsibility	Data toolbox	Comments regarding the current status
	Living Conditions (SILC)	EU/global	Yes	WU/WR	maybe	Aim to add a selection of macro-indicators to MAGNET and (experimental) try to develop a microsimulation model to do this at household level for selected countries (and possibly NUTS level).
3.3 & 7.2	Food Consumption Household budget service, HBS	EU/global	Yes	WU/WR	Not yet decided	The EU statistics on income and living conditions (EU-SILC) aim to collect timely and comparable cross-sectional and longitudinal data on income, poverty, social exclusion, and living conditions ¹ . Household budget surveys (HBSs) are national surveys focusing mainly on household expenditure on goods and services. Their main aim (especially at national level) is to calculate weights for the consumer price index ² .

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/european-union-statistics-on-income-and-living-conditions>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/household-budget-survey>

3.1 & 3.2	Farm income distribution	regional	Yes	TI	yes	The micro database on economic performance in the agricultural domain is the farm accountancy data network (FADN). It monitors farm' income and business activities. It is also an important informative source for understanding the impact of the measures taken under the CAP. FADN is the only survey of microeconomic data based on harmonized bookkeeping principles across Europe. All relevant documents and information on FADN are accessible in CIRCABC in a public domain area. As bookkeeping principles are evolving the documentations also changes. The newest document for the description of the catalogue of variables was provided in May 2023 for the farm return in 2021 but also older versions are available.
7.1	Employment	Farm types across Eu regions	Yes	WR	Yes	The FADN data include also data on labor input at farm level (standard results 10-22). This data will be compared with the labor requirements for farm operations from the FarmDyn model, which will be adjusted for the different farm types across the EU. In combination with the weights of the FADN farms in the general population, this database can be used to inform other models about regional and national changes in farm labor uses.
7.1	Food, nutrition, health	?	?	UOXF	maybe	New modelling tool and data base for analyzing the health, environmental and affordability implications of diets and dietary change.
7.3	Others (Gender, education and R&D)	EU	no	CITA, WR	Maybe	We aim to add indicators on gender (CITA) and ag R&D (WR) as well as possible time series data on a series of drivers which will be used in the econometric exercise. At the current time, a selection of these indicators

						(which at least in some cases, will most likely be taken from the Eurostat SDG database) and their drivers has not yet been determined.
	Consumer patterns (focus groups)	Country CZE, ITA, GER	yes	UCSC/CZU /UBO		We aim to study consumer preferences and the WTP for innovative, sustainable and healthy food – (milk – conventional vs. environmentally sustainable alternatives)

Table 3. Overview of Task 2.2: Database and Monitoring System for SAFE Space across spatial scales – Novel spatial data for agricultural structure

Task	Data or processes required for evidence on SJOS	Resolution	Work started	Responsibility	Data toolbox	Comments regarding the current status
3.1 3.2	Parcel Segmentation	field and parcel level	x	TI/UBO	yes (Tidex Geonode)	<p>Effective monitoring of agricultural lands requires accurate spatial information about the locations and boundaries of agricultural fields. Through satellite imagery, such information can be mapped on a large scale at a high temporal frequency. Various methods exist in the literature for segmenting agricultural fields from satellite images. Edge-based, region-based, or hybrid segmentation methods are traditional methods that have widely been used for segmenting agricultural fields. Lately, the use of deep neural networks (DNNs) for various tasks in remote sensing has been gaining traction. Therefore, to identify the optimal method for segmenting agricultural fields from satellite images, we evaluated three state-of-the-art DNNs, namely Mask R-CNN, U-Net, and FracTAL ResUNet against the multiresolution segmentation (MRS) algorithm, which is a region-based and a more traditional segmentation method. DNNs, particularly FracTAL ResUNet, can be effectively used for large-scale segmentation of agricultural fields from satellite images (Tetteh et al., 2023).</p> <p>For Germany 2016-2022</p>
3.1 3.2	Field Structural Change	communes or grid level (tbd)	yes	UBO	likely not	<p>For Germany NRW, NI, BR using LPIS (maybe entire Germany using parcel segmentation).</p> <p>The Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) is a key component of Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS). It is system based on ortho-imagery (aerial or satellite photographs) which</p>

						records all agricultural parcels in the Member States. It serves two main purposes: to clearly locate all eligible agricultural land contained within reference parcels and to calculate their maximum eligible area. Reference parcels are a uniquely identified and geographically delimited agricultural area. The Agricultural parcel system: which covers a single field and a single farmer; cadastral parcel: which can relate to one or more farmers, based on ownership, and can cover one or more crops; farmer's block: which belong to a farmer but covers one or more crops without natural boundaries and physical and topographical block which Area bordered by certain features (ditches, hedges, walls, etc.) and can cover one or more crop groups (ECA, 2016).
3.1 3.2	Crop Rotation	field and parcel level	yes	UBO	tbd	For Germany NRW using LPIS (maybe entire Germany using crop type). LPIS description as above.
3.1, 3.2	Crop type		Yes	TI/UBO	zenodo	Based on the multi-year dataset we mapped major crop sequences of cereals and leaf crops. Most crop sequences were dominated by winter cereals followed by summer cereals. Monocultures of summer cereals were mainly revealed in the Northwest of Germany. We showcased that high spatial and thematic detail in combination with annual mapping will stimulate research on crop cycles and studies to assess the impact of environmental policies on management decisions. Our results demonstrate the capabilities of integrated optical time series and SAR data in combination with variables describing local and seasonal environmental conditions for annual large-area crop type mapping (Blickensdörfer et al., 2022). Foreseen for 2000-2022.
3.1, 3.2	Grassland Intensity		Yes	TI/UBO	https://atlas.thuene.n.de/atlas/ferne rkundungsatlas	Spatially explicit knowledge on grassland extent and management is critical to understand and monitor the impact of grassland use intensity on ecosystem services and biodiversity. While regional

						<p>studies allow detailed insights into land use and ecosystem service interactions, information on a national scale can aid biodiversity assessments. However, for most European countries this information is not yet widely available. We used an analysis-ready-data cube that contains dense time series of co-registered Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 data, covering the extent of Germany. We propose an algorithm that detects mowing events in the time series based on residuals from an assumed undisturbed phenology, as an indicator of grassland use intensity (Schwieder et al., 2022).</p> <p>Foreseen for Germany 2016-2022.</p>
3.2, 6.x	Fuse of economic FADN data			TI/UBO		<p>In collaboration with LAMASUS Task 3.1/3.2/3.3. The method developed by Kempen et al. (2011) for the EU is particularly relevant, where farms in the FADN sample are linked to their environmental endowment (climate, soil attributes ...) at the EU-wide scale using a constraint optimization approach. The locations of farms from the FADN are estimated using small-scale spatial units with homogenous conditions for farming, also known as Farm Mapping units (FMU). The spatial unit aggregated the so-called homogenous mapping units (HSMU), which are defined as areas within an administrative unit with homogeneous location factors (Leip et al., 2008). A statistical approach was employed to allocate land use shares and expected crop yields to each HSMU. This method combined grid-based land use data with available aggregate information at the regional level.</p>
3.1	Linking FADN and LPIS data	Country level (CZE)	no	CZU		<p>Approved by country FADN representative. We aim to link the FADN with LPIS data to study crop rotation and crop diversity/Biodiversity (potential to link with dataset on Biodiversity)</p>

The tables show the task number in the first column, the second column describes the data needed, what kind of SJOS evidence is collected or produced (“Data Needs, Evidence on SJOS”). The scale of the data ranges from global and country data down to field-level data in some countries (third column). One can see that as of the survey date, almost all partners started their work (fourth column). The responsible partners for each of the preparation steps in each row are depicted in column five. There are already some results – in this case, data sets produced that can be used to analyze some phenomena on some indicator of SJOS – parcel segmentation data, grassland management intensity, and crop types. The parcel segmentation and the crop type data are published to be visually inspected via GEONODE, whereas the grassland intensity data is published at Zenodo (column six and seven).

This work package, WP2, is ongoing, as is the work description, tools, and results produced. Later, the platform will have all the relevant information for the BRIGHTSPACE database and monitoring system.

3. REQUIREMENTS FOR THE BRIGHTSPACE DATABASE AND MONITORING SYSTEM

In many projects, data has been collected, categorized, normalized, and stored as a copy in various database systems. Such data collection is time-consuming and often no longer up to date when creating and filling the data structure. In addition, much of the data in BRIGHTSPACE is available at different aggregation levels. Some data has a very aggregated spatial dimension, such as a 10x 10 km grid, or is based on administrative units such as a country, county, or municipality. In addition, the data points can be lost at different spatial resolutions. For example, the farm structure survey is available every five years in Germany and annually in the Netherlands.

In contrast, data from remote sensing cloud-free images are available almost daily throughout Europe. Breaking down the data to a standardized lowest denominator in time and space makes little technical sense when considering that many biodiversity indicators are available on a very small scale and over several years. Aggregating the data is also not a suitable approach, as this means that information is no longer available as it would have been in the original data.

In the BRIGHTSPACE project, the existing data sources are not combined in a new unique database but categorized, described, and referenced to the original data source using various platforms such as Git, Observable, DokuWiki, etc. Where interfaces exist, these are referenced, and use cases are documented. In addition to the interface's documentation, use case documentation is also important. It should use examples to show how the functions can be used. For example, for FADN, how do we use the API to merge or convert, load or select, and filter data records? The interface should provide a dummy data set for testing when the data is unavailable. It should indicate the software configuration it was developed under and the database version it was tested with, as well as provide links to understand the data elements. Additionally, it needs to include metadata, version information, affiliations, and references to scientific publications. Supporting unit tests and maintaining a high level of modularization is also essential.

A well-functioning platform, like Git or Observable, could be the basis for the BRIGHTSPACE monitoring system. To find a suitable selection for the different data sources, we will briefly discuss various properties in this chapter, such as the fact that the platform can store large data sets, provide visualization, access rights, etc., and examine each available platform for these properties. This allows us to assign the datasets for the monitoring database from Table 1 -3, such as georeferenced, publicly accessible, with or without metadata catalog, to the platforms with this functionality.

A data platform for the project is a comprehensive solution for capturing, processing, analyzing, and presenting data generated by modern digital businesses' systems, processes, and infrastructures. Key features that an effective data platform should have:

Comprehensiveness: What different **data types** and structures across the project can be managed? This includes relevant IT (code) and technical operational data (metadata). A single platform cannot integrate data from almost any source without adding complexity. **Storage Limitations** shall also be accounted for, such as coverage of **scripting languages** (R, Python, Javascript, markup).

Centralization: A good data platform avoids data silos and provides a **single platform** that can be used across the project. This provides actionable insights based on a **holistic view of the data**.

Availability: Data platforms make data available (**visualization**), enabling computing capabilities with automatic scalability. **Versioning** (Tracking changes in the context) and **user management** (Tracking user records) are essential for transparent and easy access. Also important is whether the platform is **open and accessible** (no payment or licensing) and how far collaborative development is possible.

Security and privacy: A data platform should provide robust **security mechanisms** to ensure data confidentiality, integrity, and availability. It should have restricted areas where necessary to give the partners ownership or access rights to maintain their field of work regarding SJOS topics. They are responsible and will be part of the platform for all available (visual). As a lot of data used for producing results in this project is protected, the rules of handling this data are very strict, and need to be allowed to put them on the platform quickly. The produced results are thoroughly checked to ensure they meet data protection rules.

Categorization: Meta data and categorization of the data by thematic fields (organize data domains)

Simplicity: A software solution is key to its effectiveness and user-friendliness. Here are some aspects that make up the simplicity of a software solution for a data platform:

- **Ease of access.** A simple software solution allows users to quickly access the needed functions without struggling through complex menus or processes.
- **Clarity and comprehensibility:** Simple software presents information and options clearly and understandably. Users should not have to guess how to perform specific tasks.
- **Minimize complexity:** A suitable software solution keeps complexity to a minimum. This means it offers only the necessary functions without additional or overloaded interfaces.
- **Intuitive user interface:** The user interface should be intuitively designed so that users can work productively without extensive training
Efficiency: Simple software allows users to complete tasks efficiently without wasting time on unnecessary steps.
- **Ease of maintenance:** A simple solution is easy to maintain and update. Complex software can lead to higher maintenance costs.

4. EXISTING (DATA) PLATFORMS: AN OVERVIEW

The database and monitoring system is a central repository for project-related information, facilitating data storage, retrieval, and analysis. By leveraging Git, Observable, DokuWiki, an Open-source Geospatial Content Management, and Zenodo, the system ensures efficient version control, real-time visualization of numerical and rather small-scale results, collaborative documentation, real-time-visualization of geospatial data, and open access of data of any kind.

4.1. GIT³

Git, a distributed version control system renowned for its robust capabilities, is a cornerstone tool in modern software development practices. By meticulously tracking changes in any set of computer files, Git empowers teams of programmers to seamlessly coordinate their efforts, particularly during collaborative software development endeavors. Its core objectives encompass speed, data integrity, and support for distributed, non-linear workflows, facilitating thousands of parallel branches running on different computers.

One of Git's paramount advantages lies in its adeptness at tracking changes to files, a functionality crucial for enabling multiple developers to collaborate on projects efficiently. By meticulously recording modifications over time, Git provides a comprehensive history of project evolution, facilitating seamless collaboration and fostering a shared understanding of codebase alterations. This robust version tracking capability enhances project transparency and enables teams to easily roll back to previous versions, mitigating the risk of unintended changes and ensuring project stability.

Furthermore, Git's support for branching and merging represents a pivotal aspect of its functionality, facilitating parallel development and fostering a conducive environment for experimentation and innovation. By creating distinct branches, developers can work on features or fixes in isolation, safeguarding the stability of the main codebase. Subsequently, the seamless merging of these branches back into the main codebase enables incorporating diverse contributions while preserving project integrity.

Nevertheless, it is essential to acknowledge that Git's comprehensive feature set may pose a learning curve for new users, particularly those unaccustomed to version control concepts. Navigating Git's intricacies necessitates a fundamental understanding of its principles and workflows, which may require initial investment in learning and training. However, despite this initial complexity, the benefits offered by Git in terms of ensuring data integrity and facilitating collaborative workflows far outweigh the challenges posed by its learning curve.

In essence, Git is an indispensable tool in the arsenal of modern software development, empowering teams to effectively manage project evolution, collaborate seamlessly, and drive innovation. Its ability to track changes, support branching for parallel development, and ensure data integrity epitomize its significance in fostering efficient and productive software development practices. Despite its initial learning curve, Git remains a cornerstone technology in collaborative programming, facilitating the realization of ambitious software projects with unparalleled efficiency and reliability.

4.2. Observable⁴

Observable, heralded as an interactive notebook platform, transcends conventional boundaries by offering a comprehensive suite of tools tailored for creating and disseminating data visualizations,

³ <https://git-scm.com>

⁴ <https://observablehq.com>

interactive documents, and code snippets. Its innovative features, coupled with its user-friendly interface, position it as a pivotal asset in the realm of data exploration and analysis.

At the heart of Observable's appeal lies its real-time visualization capabilities, which empower users to immerse themselves in dynamic data representations. By providing an intuitive environment for exploring datasets, Observable facilitates a deeper understanding of complex phenomena and empowers users to derive actionable insights. Whether unraveling intricate patterns or dissecting trends, Observable offers a dynamic canvas for interrogating data and unraveling its underlying narratives.

Moreover, Observable's collaborative power is exemplified through its shared notebook functionality, which fosters seamless teamwork and knowledge exchange. Through shared notebooks, users can collaboratively edit code in real time, enabling real-time collaboration and facilitating collective problem-solving. This collaborative ethos not only accelerates project development but also cultivates a sense of camaraderie among team members, fostering a culture of collaboration and innovation.

Additionally, Observable's emphasis on rapid prototyping enables users to iterate on ideas swiftly and experiment with diverse approaches. By providing a sandbox environment for code experimentation and visualization creation, Observable empowers users to refine their concepts and solutions iteratively. This iterative approach accelerates the development cycle and fosters a culture of experimentation and innovation, driving continuous improvement and refinement.

Observable can implement several software and programming languages, such as JavaScript, Python, R, or SQL, enabling many developers to use this platform and present their results.

4.3. DokuWiki⁵

DokuWiki stands as a beacon of simplicity and versatility in collaborative documentation, offering a lightweight yet powerful solution for teams seeking to document their projects effectively. Born from the ethos of simplicity and accessibility, DokuWiki embodies the essence of user-friendliness, making it an ideal choice for both technical and non-technical users alike.

Central to DokuWiki's appeal is its straightforward syntax and intuitive interface, which lower the barrier to entry for content creation and editing. Unlike cumbersome documentation platforms that inundate users with complex markup languages, DokuWiki embraces simplicity, allowing users to focus on conveying their ideas rather than grappling with convoluted formatting rules. This simplicity accelerates the content creation process and empowers users to collaborate seamlessly, fostering a culture of knowledge sharing and innovation.

Moreover, DokuWiki's innate ability to track page changes serves as a testament to its commitment to data integrity and version control. By automatically recording modifications over time, DokuWiki provides users with a safety net, enabling them to revert to previous versions if necessary. This version history feature instills confidence in users and facilitates iterative improvements, ensuring that project documentation remains accurate and up-to-date.

Furthermore, DokuWiki's extensibility through plugins broadens its utility, allowing users to tailor the platform to their specific needs and preferences. Whether embedding multimedia content or integrating with external services, DokuWiki's plugin ecosystem enhances its functionality, empowering users to enrich their documentation with diverse multimedia elements and streamline their workflows with seamless integrations.

However, it is essential to acknowledge that while DokuWiki excels in promoting knowledge sharing and collaboration, it may need to include some of the advanced features found in more

⁵ <https://www.dokuwiki.org/dokuwiki>

comprehensive documentation platforms. Unlike certain wiki platforms that offer real-time collaboration features out of the box, DokuWiki prioritizes simplicity and versatility, making it an ideal choice for projects where ease of use and accessibility take precedence over advanced functionality.

In essence, DokuWiki's simplicity, versatility, and commitment to user-friendliness make it a compelling choice for teams seeking to document their projects effectively. By fostering a culture of collaboration and knowledge sharing, DokuWiki empowers teams to unlock their full potential and drive meaningful outcomes, laying the groundwork for success in today's fast-paced digital landscape.

4.4. Vitepress⁶

VitePress is a Static Site Generator (SSG) designed for building fast, content-centric websites. In a nutshell, VitePress takes your source content written in Markdown, applies a theme, and generates static HTML pages that can be easily deployed anywhere.

VitePress ships with a default theme designed for technical documentation. It powers the documentation for Vite, Rollup, Pinia, VueUse, Vitest, D3, UnoCSS, Iconify, and many more.

The official Vue.js documentation is also based on VitePress but uses a custom theme shared between multiple translations.

VitePress supports fully customized themes with the developer experience of a standard Vite + Vue application. Building on Vite also means directly leveraging Vite plugins from its rich ecosystem. In addition, VitePress provides flexible APIs to load data (local or remote) and dynamically generate routes at build time. You can use it to build almost anything if the data can be determined at build time.

VitePress aims to provide an outstanding Developer Experience (DX) when working with Markdown content.

- Vite-Powered: instant server start, with edits always instantly reflected (<100ms) without page reload.
- Built-in Markdown Extensions: Frontmatter, tables, syntax highlighting... you name it. Specifically, VitePress provides many advanced features for working with code blocks, making it ideal for highly technical documentation.
- Vue-Enhanced Markdown: each Markdown page is also a Vue Single-File Component, thanks to the Vue template's 100% syntax compatibility with HTML. Using Vue templating features or imported Vue components, you can embed interactivity in your static content.

Unlike many traditional SSGs, where each navigation results in a full page reload, a website generated by VitePress serves static HTML on the initial visit. Still, it becomes a Single- (SPA) for subsequent navigation within the site. This model provides an optimal balance for performance.

- Fast initial load: The initial visit to any page will be served with static, pre-rendered HTML for fast loading speed and optimal SEO. The page then loads a JavaScript bundle that turns it into a Vue SPA („hydration“). Contrary to common assumptions of slow SPA hydration, this process is extremely fast, thanks to Vue 3's raw performance and compiler optimizations. On page speed insights, typical VitePress sites achieve near-perfect performance scores even on low-end mobile devices with a slow network.
- Fast post-load navigation: More importantly, the SPA model leads to a better user experience after the initial load. Subsequent navigation within the site will no longer cause a full page reload. Instead, the incoming page's content will be fetched and dynamically updated.

⁶ <https://vitepress.dev>

VitePress also automatically pre-fetches page chunks for links within the viewport. In most cases, post-load navigation will feel instant.

- Interactivity without penalty: To hydrate the dynamic Vue parts embedded inside static Markdown, each Markdown page is processed as a Vue component and compiled into JavaScript. This may sound inefficient, but the Vue compiler is smart enough to separate the static and dynamic parts, minimizing the hydration cost and payload size. The static parts are automatically eliminated from the JavaScript payload for the initial page load and skipped during hydration.

4.5. Open-Source Geospatial Content Management⁷

Open-source geospatial content management systems (GeoCMS) are pivotal tools in the world of geographic information systems (GIS) and spatial data infrastructures (SDI). These platforms are designed to manage, publish, and share geospatial data, enabling users to create interactive maps and perform complex spatial analyses. One of the leading examples of such systems is GeoNode, which exemplifies the capabilities and potential of open-source GeoCMS.

GeoNode⁸ is a web-based application platform for developing GIS and deploying SDI. It is built on mature and stable open-source software projects. It provides a consistent and easy-to-use interface that allows even non-specialized users to share data and create interactive maps. GeoNode's data management tools support the integrated creation of data, metadata, and map visualizations, ensuring that each system dataset can be publicly shared or restricted to specific users.

The system's social features, like user profiles, commenting, and rating systems, foster the development of communities around each platform, facilitating the use, management, and quality control of the data the GeoNode instance contains. Moreover, GeoNode is designed to be a flexible platform that software developers can extend, modify, or integrate to meet the requirements of their applications.

A GeoCMS like GeoNode is not just about data sharing; it's also about data preservation. By providing a stable and citable platform for geospatial artifacts, GeoNode ensures the long-term preservation of scientific knowledge. Each dataset is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), which provides a persistent link to the material, ensuring that it can be referenced and cited in other works.

GeoNode's open-source nature means that it is free to use and redistribute under the terms of the GNU General Public License. This has significant implications for democratizing geospatial data, as it removes financial barriers to entry and allows for widespread adoption and customization.

The benefits of using an open-source GeoCMS like GeoNode are manifold. It promotes collaboration and transparency in the research process, encourages the sharing of methodologies and underlying data, and supports the principles of Open Science. By enabling researchers and practitioners to manage and share large volumes of data and software, GeoNode plays a critical role in various applications, including environmental monitoring, urban planning, and resource management.

In conclusion, open-source geospatial content management systems significantly advance geospatial data management. Platforms like GeoNode are at the forefront of this movement, providing powerful tools that are accessible, user-friendly, and integral to the collaborative and transparent sharing of geospatial data. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, these systems will undoubtedly play a crucial role in shaping the future of geospatial data analysis and dissemination.

⁷ <https://genode.org>

⁸ <https://docs.geonode.org/en/master/about/index.html>.

4.6. Zenodo⁹

Zenodo is a free and open-access repository that has become a cornerstone for researchers worldwide. Developed under the European OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe) program and operated by CERN, It is a general-purpose repository that allows researchers to deposit a wide range of research outputs, from research papers and datasets to research software and reports.

Platform 3 was launched in May 2013 to support open access and open data movements in Europe. It was designed to be a catch-all repository for EC-funded research, but its scope quickly expanded to accommodate research from all over the world and every discipline. Zenodo’s inclusive approach does not impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions, or license, eliminating barriers to adopting data-sharing practices.

Zenodo’s commitment to Open Science is evident in its ability to handle all the digital artifacts necessary for fully understanding and reproducing research. This includes not just the core data and software supporting publications but also materials associated with conferences, projects, or institutions themselves. Zenodo’s flexibility is one of its key strengths, allowing researchers to deposit content that can be closed, restricted, or embargoed and then made openly available later in the research workflow.

The platform’s user-friendly interface is complemented by a rich API, which enables third-party tools and services to integrate with Zenodo. This makes Zenodo a versatile backend for various workflows. Zenodo is an essential tool for researchers who must manage and share large volumes of data and software.

Zenodo also plays a critical role in preserving scientific knowledge. Providing a stable and citable platform for research artifacts ensures that scientific research outputs are preserved for the long term. Each deposit on Zenodo is assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), which provides a persistent link to the material, ensuring that it can be referenced and cited in other works.

The platform’s dedication to Open Science extends beyond just providing a repository. Zenodo actively promotes collaboration and transparency in the research process. It encourages researchers to share their final results and the underlying data and methodologies, fostering a culture of openness and reproducibility in science.

Zenodo stands out as a beacon of Open Science, offering a robust, flexible, and user-friendly platform for researchers to share and preserve their work. Its no-barrier policy on data sharing and the backing of CERN and the European OpenAIRE program make it a trusted and valuable resource for the global research community.

4.7. Overview of key features and data platforms

Table 4 shows an overview of key features and the (data) platforms and how and if these features are met by the platforms.

Table 4. Overview of key features and data platforms

	Gitlab	Observable	Doku Wiki	Vitepress	GeoNode	Zenodo
Data Types	All	CSV, SQL	TXT	MARKDOWN	Geospatial data	All

⁹ <https://zenodo.org>

Storage Limitations	Depends	Free-tier accounts	Depends	Depends	Depends	No limitation
Script languages	any executable language	JavaScript	PHP	JavaScript	Geospatial data	languages capable of HTTP request
Single platform			x	x		
Holistic view of the data			x	x		
Visualization		x	x	x	x	
Versioning	x		x	x		
User management	x	x	x	x	x	x
Open and feely accessible			x	x	x	x
Security mechanisms	Access Control	Notebook Sharing and Permissions	Access Control Lists	Content Security Policy	Spatial Data Security	DOI (Digital Object Identifiers) Privacy
Meta Data	Repository Organization	Notebook Tags	Namespaces	Markdown files	Organize geospatial layers and datasets	Keywords/Subjects
Ease of access			x	x		x
Clarity and comprehensibility			x	x		x
Minimize complexity			x			x
Intuitive user interface		x	x	x		x
Ease of maintenance						
<i>x = good</i>						

5. GENERAL IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

5.1. Implementation for the open data

The implementation begins with the crucial step of selecting the most suitable documentation platform. DokuWiki and WordPress will undergo thorough screening to assess their usability, accessibility, security, and productivity features. Once chosen, this documentation platform will be established as the central repository for project-related information.

User partners responsible for specific data sets or indicators are invited to contribute content to the platform. They will have the autonomy to produce and publish their content, ensuring a collaborative approach to information dissemination.

A dedicated GIT page will be established to foster collaboration and code sharing among partners. This platform will serve as a centralized hub for version control and collaborative coding efforts, facilitating efficient coordination and sharing of software development efforts.

Existing results, data, and code will take precedence in the platform's initial implementation phase. This approach allows partners to leverage existing resources, accelerating the platform's development. Additionally, it allows partners to familiarize themselves with the platform's functionalities and allows external stakeholders to gain insights into the project's progress.

All partners are encouraged to contribute content to the documentation platform actively. By promoting widespread participation, the platform can evolve into a comprehensive resource that reflects all project stakeholders' collective expertise and efforts.

Embracing the ethos of a "living document", the documentation platform will continually evolve and adapt to reflect the latest developments and insights within the project. By fostering a dynamic and collaborative environment, the platform will serve as a dynamic knowledge repository, ensuring its relevance and utility throughout the project's lifecycle.

Table 5. Proposal of an implementation plan for the open data

Task	Data or processes required for evidence on SJOS	Git	Observable	Open-Source Geospatial Content Management	Zenodo
4.2	Non-tariff measures				x
3.3	Food Waste/Losses along the supply chain		optional		x
	Organic farming (SDGs)		optional		x
3.3	Dietary developments				optional
	Biodiversity, Water, Nitrogen	x			optional

	Living conditions	x			
3.3 & 7.2	Food consumption (major food groups) SILC/Household budget service, HBS	x			x
3.1 & 3.2	Farm income distribution	x			x
7.1	Employment	x			x
7.1	Food, nutrition, health	x			x
7.2	Others (Gender, education and R&D)	x			x
	Consumer patterns (focus groups)	x			x
3.1 3.2	Parcel segmentation	x		x	x
3.1 3.2	Field structural change	x		x	x
3.1 3.2	Crop rotation	x		x	x
3.1, 3.2	Crop type	x		x	x
3.1, 3.2	Grassland intensity	x		x	x
3.2 6.x	Fuse of economic FADN data	x			x
3.1	Linking FADN and LPIS data	x			x

5.2. Implementation for the BrightSpace Database and Monitoring system

In alignment with the conceptual framework presented in this deliverable, the newly developed system leverages a suite of tools designed to seamlessly integrate both existing and newly acquired or developed databases according to the SJOS indicators. This approach is distinctive within the BrightSpace project because it goes beyond conventional data collection and storage practices. Instead, the system's architecture focuses on establishing a "custom database" that actively facilitates

the interoperability of various platforms and tools, ensuring they operate in harmony to fulfill the project's specific objectives.

To achieve this, the partners collaborating within Work Package 2 (WP2) are collectively developing a system tailored to meet these requirements. This means, Thünen will come up with a few examples on how the system will be established. Partners will then, depending on their progress, edit their entries regarding their work on tools, explanations, articles, code or data for different indicators. If help is needed, Thünen will assist bilaterally with partners. As an example, Figure 1 describes the scheme of how the system is foreseen to work. A landing page with links to the BrightSpace indicators. Depending on the progress of partners working on indicators, different information will be provided. Beginning with a description of what is presented for the indicator, links to reports, articles or data are also provided. This should give the user the opportunity to get all the information that is needed and even further information about where additional information is stored. There might be more than one entry per indicator.

Figure 1. Scheme of BrightSpace database and monitoring system

This system will allow users to effortlessly access relevant data needed to engage with the SJOS indicators, ensuring that the information is both accessible and actionable. A user entering the system can select a particular indicator and, in doing so, will have access to a broad range of associated information. This includes detailed descriptions, references to articles or reports, links to blogs, code examples, and access to related datasets.

Furthermore, this system is designed as an editable platform, granting contributors within WP2 the ability to add, modify, and refine the data as necessary. Its structure promotes longevity and adaptability, enabling it to function as a "living document" that can evolve in step with the project's progress. Importantly, this adaptability also ensures that the system can be maintained and further updated even after the project's formal conclusion, supporting ongoing research and applications aligned with the BrightSpace objectives.

Moreover, this approach aims to establish a more sustainable and enduring solution compared to previous data collection and development efforts, which frequently fell into disuse once the project ended. Unlike these former systems, which were often developed in isolation and lacked integration with other tools or datasets, the current approach is designed to align closely with the BrightSpace SJOS indicators, promoting synergy across existing and newly created databases. By building an

interconnected system that integrates a wide range of tools and resources, we are laying the groundwork for a platform that will remain valuable and functional well beyond the life of the project.

This system's design intentionally prioritizes long-term utility and accessibility, encouraging stakeholders to continue engaging with the data and tools after the project's official end. Through these mechanisms, the platform is set to become a dynamic resource, evolving and growing over time rather than becoming obsolete. By offering structured support for ongoing use and periodic updates, we intend for this system to outlast prior, limited solutions and provide lasting contributions to the research community and stakeholders who rely on SJOS indicators and related data.

In summary, this paragraph has outlined the conceptual foundation and design principles guiding the development of the BrightSpace Database and monitoring system. By establishing a sustainable, integrated platform for SJOS indicators, we aim to overcome the limitations of previous data systems, ensuring continued usability and relevance well beyond the project's lifespan.

The upcoming tasks, specifically Tasks 2.2 and 2.3, focus on building and refining the BrightSpace Database and the monitoring system prototype, with an emphasis on adaptability across both the SAFE and JUST OS frameworks and across multiple spatial scales. This development process will unfold over the coming months, with the prototype expected to reach an initial version by month 24. Subsequent refinements will continue, leading to the completion of Deliverable D2.2 by month 36, at which point the database and monitoring system will be fully operational.

These next phases will be crucial in realizing the project's objectives, as they will translate the conceptual plans discussed here into a robust, user-centered system. This system is designed not only to meet the immediate needs of the BrightSpace project but also to provide a resilient, long-term resource that will support the research and data management needs of the community well into the future.

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